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PhD 16 - Codes4strain

Responsible Partner: Institut Pasteur

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D-PHD16-4.7

Integration of MLSL identifiers into the BIGSdb platform to make them publicly available

Extract from the preprint (1):

The MLSL nomenclature was incorporated into the Institut Pasteur *K. pneumoniae* MLST and whole genome MLST database (<https://bigsdb.pasteur.fr/klebsiella>) under the classification schemes functionality developed in BIGSdb version 1.21.0. In brief, the cgMLST profile of all isolates with fewer than 30 missing scgMLSTv2 alleles were assigned to a core genome sequence type (cgST), and these were grouped into single-linkage partitions for each of the 10 classification levels. For SLs and CGs, a custom classification group field (named SL or CG within the system) was additionally populated with identifiers inherited from 7-gene MLST. All cgMLST profiles and classification identifiers are freely available to use, open access.

To allow users to identify users to identify *K. pneumoniae* isolates easily, a profile matching functionality was developed, allowing to search for cgMLST profiles related to a query genome sequence. This was implemented and is available from the website sequence query page (<https://bigsdb.readthedocs.io/en/latest/administration.html#scheme-profile-clustering-setting-up-classification-schemes>). This functionality returns the classification identifiers (including MLST-inherited CG and SL identifiers) of the cgMLST profile that is most closely related to the query genomic sequence, along with its number of mismatches compared to the closest profile.

References:

- (1) A dual barcoding approach to bacterial strain nomenclature: Genomic taxonomy of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains | bioRxiv. Melanie Hennart, Julien Guglielmini, Martin C.J. Maiden, Keith A. Jolley, Alexis Criscuolo, Sylvain Brisse
bioRxiv 2021.07.26.453808; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.07.26.453808>

Example for the *K. pneumoniae* reference strains used in the manuscript (1):

						MLSL classification groups									
Taxonomic Designation	Phylogroup	ID	Strain bank ID	ST (MLST)	scgST (scgMLST629_S)	klebs_species_v1.0	klebs_subspecies_v1.0	klebs_sublineage_v1.0	klebs_clonalgroup_v1.0	klebs_threshold10_v1.0	klebs_threshold7_v1.0	klebs_threshold4_v1.0	klebs_threshold2_v1.0	klebs_threshold1_v1.0	klebs_threshold0_v1.0
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	250	SB1067	17	4	1	1	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	1546	SB132	3	13	1	1	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	25	SB107	38	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	252	SB1139	37	5	1	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	412	SB617	55	8	1	1	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	10	SB20	15	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	408	SB612	133	7	1	1	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	1761	SB4938	442	17	1	1	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	398	SB3928	23	6	1	1	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	1509	SB4496	380	11	1	1	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>quasipneumoniae</i>	Kp2	6432	SB11	1528	32	1	1	32	32	32	32	32	32	32	32
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>quasipneumoniae</i>	Kp2	3884	SB2110	526	21	1	1	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	21
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>quasipneumoniae</i>	Kp2	1555	SB59	1118	15;5002	1	1	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>quasipneumoniae</i>	Kp2	3882	SB98	622	20	1	1	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>variicola</i>	Kp3	3881	SB1	2273	19	1	4	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>variicola</i>	Kp3	3880	SB48	2263	18	1	4	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>variicola</i>	Kp3	1512	SB579	146	12	1	4	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>variicola</i>	Kp3	7932	SB4767	1220	35	1	4	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35

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<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>similipneumoniae</i>	Kp4	49	SB164	414	3	1	1	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>similipneumoniae</i>	Kp4	3885	SB203	384	22	1	1	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>similipneumoniae</i>	Kp4	1554	SB30	1215	14;5015	1	1	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>similipneumoniae</i>	Kp4	3886	SB4697	2275	23	1	1	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>similipneumoniae</i>	Kp4	3887	SB610	2276	24	1	1	24	24	24	24	24	24	24	24
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>tropica</i>	Kp5	1556	SB94	1216	16	1	6	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>tropica</i>	Kp5	4433	SB5387	2466	25	1	6	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>tropica</i>	Kp5	4485	SB5439	2486	26	1	6	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>tropica</i>	Kp5	4577	SB5531	2561	27	1	6	27	27	27	27	27	27	27	27
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>tropica</i>	Kp5	4590	SB5544	2605	28	1	6	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>tropica</i>	Kp5	4656	SB5610	2600	29	1	6	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29
<i>K. quasivariicola</i>	Kp6	1508	SB33	1214	10	3	3	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
<i>K. quasivariicola</i>	Kp6	1507	SB6071	1155	9;5091	3	3	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
<i>K. quasivariicola</i>	Kp6	6491	SB6094	2830	34	3	3	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34
<i>K. quasivariicola</i>	Kp6	6452	SB6095	3303	33	3	3	33	33	33	33	33	33	33	33
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	6353	SB5857	3291	31	7	8	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	5704	38679	2831	30	7	8	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	12476	FF1019	4939	41	7	8	37	37	37	38	39	40	41	41
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	12475	FF1017	4938	40	7	8	36	36	36	36	37	39	40	40
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	12474	FF1014	4938	39	7	8	36	36	36	36	37	39	39	39
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	12473	FF1011	4938	38	7	8	36	36	36	36	37	38	38	38
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	12472	FF1008	4938	37	7	8	36	36	36	36	37	37	37	37
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	12471	FF1006	4938	37	7	8	36	36	36	36	37	37	37	37
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	12470	FF1003	4938	37	7	8	36	36	36	36	37	37	37	37
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	12469	FF930	4938	36	7	8	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	36